

Working Capital Management in Hyundai Showroom Bidar

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Abstract- The running capital administration challenge of HYUNDAI MOTOR INDIA LTD transformed into a fabulous encounter. Each assembling partnership considers working capital control inconveniences consistently. Authoritative charges might be diminished and pay can easiest be extended in the event that it might oversee working capital viably. As soon on the grounds that the office can provide buyer amuse and subsequently offer essential usefulness and productivity. The executives need to rely on specific relevant data to make a dissemination of essential determinations. The records is made helpful with the guide of investigation and understanding. My test is related to research on working capital control. It changed into verified that the functioning pattern of a business undertaking turned out to be especially problematic and due to the association having a diminished running capital capacity. By utilizing a spread of estimations and breaks down and afterward making understandings with answers to specific inconveniences, I attempt to submit proposal this is applicable to the organization. In this specific situation, I use techniques and methodologies comprising of, assessing running capital, considering working cycles and utilizing various financial proportions to provide a precise image of the office. A short-term position is an extension among an association and an association. This were given me worried in a task that assisted me with advantaging a hypothetical data of reach and advantageous monetary reality. Furthermore, inside the way, I am equipped for make a commitment to the person notwithstanding the blast of the partnership.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyundai Motor Company transformed into situated in 1967 as an auxiliary of the association Hyundai Engineering and Construction. The business venture started via collecting autos and trucks for the passage

business undertaking at a vehicle fabricating office. In 1975 he created his first auto called the Hyundai Cortina which become delivered in association with the passage motorbike association. Throughout the following two years, it have become the thirteenth biggest vehicle association inside the worldwide with a 2% extent inside the overall retail market. In 1975, the organization resolved to make own vehicle would be offered under the logo call 'Hyundai. He employed 5 of the top of the line vehicle engineers inside the UK who planned his first vehicle. 'Hyundai poni. The car have become the essential advancing vehicle in South Korea due to its little length and monetary expense. Next the Hyundai bangs entered the Canadian commercial center and inside 9 months turned into the good - selling vehicle there. By 1985, creation had outperformed more noteworthy than 1, 000, 000 autos.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Seed money is employed as modern-day things or as an overabundance of current resources as opposed to modern day liabilities. Seed money control Concerned with problems that emerge while looking to regulate current resources, advanced duties and existing relational cable connections.

In any industry the working capital is most important as it plays significant role starting from procuring raw materials until it is converted into finished goods. If the working capital is under invested it results in delay in output of finished products which in turn reduces sales and profits or if it is over invested, the interest has to be paid on the amount. The payable rate of the field of working capital management, raw materials, receivables, cash and its management system is very vast.

The study has been conducted to know the working capital management of the “Hyundai showroom” to know various ratios of working capital. As working

capital is the life blood and nerve centre of an organization can run successfully without an adequate amount of working capital.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this research paper is

1. To find out and calculate the overall working capital management in selected four-wheeler company.
2. To find out the trends in working capital followed in four Wheel industry.
3. To analyze and evaluate the financial performance of selected companies in terms of working capital
4. management of automobile Sector of India.

5. To study the pattern of working capital management of Sector of India.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The study mainly deals with working capital management of HUNDAYI SHOWROOM BIDAR decision regarding working capital is not one time decision, so the scope of the study is to identify the financial performance of the company between the year 2015-20, company growth and profit earned.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

TABLE 4.1

SCHEDULE OF CHANGES IN WORKING CAPITAL FOR THE YEAR ENDING 31-03-2016 & 31-03-2017

Particulars	2016	2017	Increase in Working capital	Decrease in Working capital
<u>CURRENT ASSETS:</u>				
Cash and bank Balance	98.20	2508.50	2410.30	
Sundry debtors	809.90	824.50	14.60	
Inventories	1208.80	1415.00	206.20	
TOTALS(A)	20116.90	4748.00		
<u>CURRENT LIABILITIES:</u>				
	3160.00	3861.60		701.60
Other liabilities	3160.00	3861.60		
TOTAL(B)	-1043.10	886.40		1929.50
(A-B)	1929.50			
Increase in working capital	886.40	886.40	2631.10	2631.10

TABLE 4.2

SCHEDULE OF CHANGES IN WORKING CAPITAL FOR THE YEAR ENDING 31-03-2017 & 31-03-2018

Particulars	2017	2018	Increase in Working capital	Decrease in Working capital

CURRENT ASSETS:				
Cash and bank Balance				72.40
	2508.50	2436.10		
Sundry debtors	824.50			
		937.60	113.10	
Inventories	1415.00		381.50	
TOTAL(A)		1796.50		
CURRENT LIABILITIES:	4748.00	5170.20		
Other liabilities				
TOTAL(B)				1476.40
	3861.60	5338.00		
	3861.60	5338.00		
(A-B)				
	886.40	-167.80	1054.20	
Decrease in working capital		1054.20		
	886.40	886.40	1548.80	1548.80

TABLE 4.3

SCHEDULE OF CHANGES IN WORKING CAPITAL FOR THE YEAR ENDING 31-03-2018& 31-03-2019

Particulars	2018	2019	Increase in Working capital	Decrease in Working capital
<u>CURRENT ASSETS:</u>				
Cash and bank Balance	2436.10	775.00		1661.10
Sundry debtors	937.60	1423.70	486.10	
Inventories	1796.50	1840.70	44.20	
TOTALS(A)	5170.20	4039.40		
<u>CURRENT LIABILITIES:</u>				
Other liabilities				
TOTAL(B)	5338.00	5845.80		
	5338.00	5845.80		
(A-B)	-167.80	-1806.40	1638.60	

		1638.60		
Decrease in working capital	-167.80	-167.80	2168.90	2168.90

TABLE 4.4

SCHEDULE OF CHANGES IN WORKING CAPITAL FOR THE YEAR ENDING 31-03-2019 & 31-03-2020

Particulars	2019	2020	Increase in Working capital	Decrease in Working capital
CURRENT ASSETS:				
Cash and bank Balance				145.30
Sundry debtors	775.00	629.70		
Inventories	1423.70	1413.70		10.00
TOTALS(A) CURRENT	1840.70	1705.90		134.80
LIABILITIES:	4039.40	3749.30		
Other liabilities				
TOTAL(B)	5845.80	6996.90		1151.10
(A-B)	5845.80	6996.90		
	-1806.40	-3247.60		
Decrease in working capital		1441.20	1441.20	
	-1806.40	-1806.40	1441.20	1441.20

TABLE 4.5

SCHEDULE OF CHANGES IN WORKING CAPITAL FOR THE YEAR ENDING 31-03-2020 & 31-03-2021

Particulars	2020	2021	Increase in Working capital	Decrease in Working capital
CURRENT ASSETS:				
Cash and bank Balance				
Sundry debtors	629.70	18.30		
Inventories				611.40
TOTALS(A)	1413.70	1069.80		343.90
CURRENT LIABILITIES:	1705.90	2,615.00	909.10	
	3749.30	3703.10		

Other liabilities	6996.90	8,013.60		1016.70
TOTAL(B)	6996.90	8,013.60		
(A-B)	-3247.60	-4310.50	1062.90	
		1062.90		
Increase in working capital	-3247.60	-3247.60	1972	1972

IV. FINDINGS

1. We find that seed money for a very long time except for 2017-21 is best compelling in 2017 and the remainder of the complete years working money equilibrium is weak
2. Not There altered into best a blast in seed money in 2016-17, after having a regular lower in seed money. Consequently, we study that the venture has not kept program satisfactory state of the art what you should meet its running money wishes
3. Moreover, 2016-17 in movement of current amounts, the typical show proportion is two: 1, which signifies that advanced property should be twofold from modern-day liabilities, regarding this situation
4. An unnecessary stock turnover proportion is ideal as it recommends more remarkable deals than every rupee put resources into shares. That hence stresses that gatherings having excessive pay enhance extreme stock turnover.
5. For this situation, we track down that the stock turnover proportion is exceptionally high, certainly because of an absolutely little opportunity of offers which prompts a not - existent stock position.
6. The quick ratio indicates a good liquidity value of the company. The liquidity value for the year 2017 is the highest.
7. The working capital turnover ratio is negative in all years except 2017 and hence we observe that it has a weak velocity of utilization of working capital

V. SUGGESTIONS

1. Organizations should undertaking to keep an increment in working capital, as it's miles extremely fundamental for the successful working of the task.
2. The company has to maintain more of current assets than current liabilities to have a better working capital
3. Organizations need to save more the modern property than current commitments while going to have better seed money.
4. The working capital utilization of the company should be improvised in order to maintain efficient management of capital.
5. The stock turnover ratio is high indicating higher risk out of stock positions, hence the stock level has to be increased in order to meet the immediate requirement as a result of which profits can be increased.
6. A good working capital position of a company indicates the company's strong position in its worth, the result of which it can improve its goodwill among its investors, debtors creditors and shareholders" hence the company has to maintain a good working capital management.
7. The company should maintain working management controls in place

CONCLUSION

The above study provides us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Typically, the office has extremely enormous pay for the span of the five economic years showing an increment in call for its product in the commercial center. The business undertaking possesses an wonderful market notoriety and confirmed important expenditure scales.
2. Not Typically the organization has dreadful working capital control, which is obviously not a fine signal of the partnership's appropriately financial event. Organizations require after higher capital control to build benefits over the long run through having decent running money that follows the developing design.
3. Overall it has been a great learning experience doing this project helping me gain a deeper insight into the concept of working capital.

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